

TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES OF EFFECTIVE ONLINE SECOND/FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

This research paper discusses interactive methods of conducting online classes by using an innovative app Mentimeter: for making interactive presentation tools and to improve learning and engagement of learners` in the classroom. There are discussed quick and easy ways of formative assessment of students, creating Word Clouds and getting immediate feedback from learners during the lesson.

Introduction: “The mediocre teacher tells. The good teacher explains. The superior teacher demonstrates. The great teacher inspires.”
— William Arthur Ward

In the advanced technological world language learning and teaching also took a new phase. Classroom teaching materials and approaches also become more complex. Educators, scientists started to engage with the notion of identity, language learning and critical pedagogies. The term “pedagogy” has been changed to “Pedagogies” which include various methods of teaching and selecting the appropriate approaches and tools among different kinds based on the needs of the learners required critical

thinking skills from educators and became challengeable for them.

In the 21st century technology has become a governor in every sphere of the life as language teachers and learners have felt the relation and power of technological innovations. Especially for the last two semesters all over the world because of Pandemic students have to study online by using their cell phones or laptops. During these semesters teachers and students have witnessed frequent obstacles in teaching and learning languages such as: lack of natural interaction with teachers and peers, conducting activities and evaluating them. Online teaching also enabled easy distribution of handouts, worksheets and

controlling all students during online classes. Theoretical basis for the use of online input sessions and apps come from various sources, in other words there are not any specific pedagogical theories suggested by the use of any noble technology. (Plegrum & Plomp, 2002). The article provides sufficient information about the role of Mentimeter app in the ELT in the experience of freshman students in English language and literature department of Urgench State University. The following research article is aimed to present details on how to use technology and design materials from the scratch for using in the language classroom, which provides learners with information, practice and skills related to learning English language.

Literature review: According to Brain Tomlinson (2010) designed materials for teaching English must stimulate intellectual features of learners, achieve their curiosity and attention too. Moreover, these materials must follow the language acquisition principles of Krashen (1985) and involve authentic and emotional features to achieve the communicative purposes. The purpose from the usage of this app is to motivate the learners and encourage speaking more in target language. Also Mentimeter help learners to memorize and experiment the language in the learning process.

According to Thornberry (2005) "Puts forth the following criteria, for selecting tasks, with the aim of increasing autonomous language use. When selecting a language activity for an oral skill class, the teacher may want to consider how many of these criteria the activity fulfills". "More authentic communication is likely to occur in the classroom if students go beyond the

practice of language forms for their own sake and use their linguistic and communicative resources in order to obtain the information" (J. C. Richards, 2006a, p.18).

H. Soliemani (2016) noted in his article "The role of technology in materials development" that using technology in the language classroom is very efficient approach for both teachers and learners, according to his theory technology helps educators easily adjust or adopt the teaching materials and helps them to facilitate the learning process for example the Mentimeter app is very useful to conduct evaluation of the learners and design quizzes and presentation, moreover it improves language acquisition of the learners as youth are eager to use technology and interested in them highly, they can learn and do these tasks at home as it is very efficient way of conducting online teaching also.

Based on the LAP (language acquisition principle) 6, Tomlinson noted that materials development is deeply connected with language acquisition principles Tomlinson et al. (2001.) Based on this, this app gives an opportunity to use language in communicative purposes. Students will design dialogues and act it in the online classroom at the end of the activity they will do peer evaluation with using the spider chat. Here learners not only practice the language but also produce it. With the help of this app students are expected to be better prepared to use technology in language learning too.

Research Methodology: At the beginning for using this Mentimeter app teachers should enter www.mentimeter.com and sign up

by using email and password. 2. Then there comes a dashboard where exists an access to all features and facilities of the app. You are then prompted to choose what you will use Mentimeter mainly for:

- Workshops
- Events (10-50 people)
- Training sessions
- Education
- Meetings or team management
- Conferences or large events
- Other

There is a variety of question types you can use to poll the audience: Multiple Choice, Word Cloud, Scales, Open ended, 100 points, 2 by 2 Matrix, Who will win?

Due to the first principle of materials development-**taking free activities** in the leading stage of the lesson, such as an extensive (free without any task) listening or writing gives learners more self-confidence in the learning process. Word Cloud question is very effective for this purpose. At the beginning of the lesson play one of the famous songs (Enrique, "Somebody" or the song related to the topic you are going to present) and give a question in the cover page of the presentation "Have you ever heard this song?", let your students to vote in the word cloud.

1. Choose word cloud from the question types.

- 2.
- 3.
4. Enter the question you want to ask.
5. Decide the maximum number of entries each participant may enter to the word cloud (maximum of 10 words each person).
6. Decide which profanity filter (type of the language and access) should be used.

7. Press "Show Presentation" to start getting response from the participants.

Participants can enter through their devices to [menti.com](https://www.menti.com) by inserting the code presented by the instructor. This activity employs the learners' attention to the lesson effectively and encourages students to think and recall, this activity is designed based on the Tomlinson's text driven approach here before listening about the song students should predict the topic of the lesson, according to Bolitho (2003)

“language learners benefit from noticing the important features of the input”.

Scales-this option allows your learners rate statements on a scale from 0 through 5.

1. Choose Scales as your question type.

2. Enter the question you want to ask your audience.

3. Enter the statements that your audience can rate from 0-5.

4. In order to add another question, click the “question” button.

5. Optional: Enter short labels to explain the low and high value

6. Press to “Show Presentation”

to start getting response from the participants. After participants fill in their answers Mentimeter will immediately show the results for you to interpret.

To keep possession of effectiveness and ensure attainment of desired objectives high emphasis is put on the assessment procedure in the lesson plan. Peer feedback and peer evaluation as well as self-reflection, teacher feedback is used nearly after each activity in the lesson. Teacher’s main role is to be a facilitator during discussions, games and activities. As activities are easily evaluated by the app and students conduct peer evaluation during the online classes. The Mentimeter is suitable for adult students whose main purposes are to develop awareness of English language, especially in integrated skills. Besides providing valuable language input teaching materials should express and construct real world context too.

In order to clarify the effectiveness of the app were chosen students from UrSU (Urgench State University) the target group of learners from Foreign Philology Faculty, English language and literature department, this department is one of the prestigious departments at the University was established in 1962. Since its foundation faculty has educated more than 10 thousand English language teachers, who have significantly contributed to the improvement of the English language teaching. Mixed level English language learners, their level range from B1- pre-intermediate to B2- intermediate. Their ages range from 18 to 22 and 15 students participated in the online classes. The students’ first language is Uzbek and subject “Integrated Skills”. Overall there were conducted six lessons in Zoom for 80 minutes and in the three lessons were used app **Mentimeter** and the other three lessons were used **Power Point** presentations. In order to know the opinion of the students’ at the end of the lesson there were conducted a questionnaire in Mentimeter app to know their personal opinions about the online lessons, the questionnaire involved 15 items and asked participants to indicate their attitude towards the Mentimeter based and power point presentation lessons. According to statistical analysis 14 students from 15 considered Mentimeter based lessons more interesting,

communicative and interesting than Power Point based online lessons.

How could you evaluate mentimeter presentations and quizzes?

15 ОТВЕТОВ

The research on this article is also aimed to present some effective ways of formative assessment of EFL learners. In order to choose more effective ways and tools of assessment teachers also need to take into consideration learning strategies

of learners. In this app it's easy to use both formative and summative assessment tools with analytical rubric and checklists, moreover for each activity students can easily give feedback for evaluating their peer's performance during the lesson. By using 2 by 2 matrix questions

this type of questions allow participants to rate each other's performance while the lesson. The assessment should be based on the five principles, validity, reliability, authenticity, practicality and washback. Washback is the most important one as students should consider their marks fair so immediate assessment is also important because in Mentimeter they can see their results after each activity if they have any objections or questions they can do it during the lesson. When it comes to the videos and other digital materials using them in Mentimeter doesn't require high digital intelligence from teachers as app itself can construct them easily or there are ready pictures,

frames and gifs for using in the presentations or constructing interactive games as unique ones. From the results of survey, I can say that this presentations and tools worked well and keep the interests of the learners, moreover helped me to evaluate them easily so it gave me practicality in the evaluation authenticity and reliability of the marking criteria of the learners.

Conclusion: According to Krashen's theory of Second Language Acquisition (1988) he indicates five factors which influences in learning language and must be taken account by the instructors of the language: 1) age- he described a critical age period that till the adolescence learners

should start the language learning. 2) Native language and cultural background of the learner, 3) self-esteem, 4) anxiety, 5) attitudes and motivation, in connection to these principles he added that meaningful instructions and communicative environment is also must be considered too. The present study strived to determine the effect of teaching and learning languages in online EFL classes. With the help of the Mentimeter students will be able to feel comfortable to use expressions related to daily lives. This means that learners will acquire knowledge and skills;

- Writing (peer feedback and open-ended questions)
- Speaking (Booking tickets and analyzing the airport announcements).
- Reading (Summarizing the long texts and creating the mind maps)

The results of the survey showed that there were significant differences between

more effective and less effective teaching materials for online EFL classes. Similarly, this material is suitable for Language teachers to provide their learners with various language learning tools in one lesson that helps also to conduct differentiated tasks in order all learners can perform their language skills in the lesson. Nevertheless, it is clear that further studies are needed to deal with the investigated issue of the present study in various learning contexts.

In conclusion the usage of this app both in online and offline EFL lessons is suitable to the principles of language acquisition and materials development and aimed to prioritize the higher profile of ESL/EFL classroom. Mentimeter is an easy-to-use tool perfect for all types of learning, moreover different questions can be used in different situations and it is free.

REFERENCES:

1. Tomlinson, B. (2003). Developing principled frameworks for materials development
2. Tomlinson (Ed.) *Developing materials for language teaching* (pp. 107-129)
3. Motteram, G. (2011). Developing language learning materials with technology
4. Mukundan, J. (2008). Multimedia materials in developing countries: The Malaysian experience.
5. Hobbs, R. (2011). Research as Authentic Inquiry. *Digital and media literacy: Connecting culture and classroom* (pp. 25-46).
6. Kullman, J. (2013). Telling tales: Changing discourses of identity in the 'Global' UK- published English language coursebook
7. Darwin, R., & Norton, B. (2017). Identity, language learning, and critical pedagogies in digital times.